

EARTH OBSERVATION CLIMATE INFORMATION SERVICE

Quick Start Guide

Swansea University Climate High-resolution UK Aerosol
Optical Depth

Issued by:
Kevin Pearson and Peter North
Swansea University,
Date: 18th May 2026

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
1. Quick Start: Swansea University Climate High-resolution UK Aerosol Optical Depth	4
1.1 What products are available?	4
1.2 Summary information	4
1.2.1 Variables summary information	5
1.3 What can these products be used for?	6
1.4 Where to find these products for download	6
1.5 Using downloaded data	6
1.5.1 Import Data	6
1.5.2 Data Reduction/Subsetting	7
1.5.3 Re-Gridding/Formatting	7
1.5.4 Forming a Time-series	8
1.5.5 Displaying Data	9
1.6 Your obligations when using these products	11
History of modifications / Change Log	12
Related Documents / Reference Documents	12
Acronyms and/or Abbreviations	12
General definitions	12

1. Quick Start: Swansea University Climate High-resolution UK Aerosol Optical Depth

The following will provide you with sufficient information to quickly get to grips with the Swansea University, Climate High-Resolution United Kingdom, Aerosol Optical Depth dataset products and to gain some familiarity with the information available.

1.1 What products are available?

These data are derived from Swansea University Global Aerosol retrievals (v1.14) for the Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometers (SLSTR) on the Sentinel-3A and Sentinel-3B satellites. Original level 2 retrievals in the UK region have been reprojected from the instrument swath onto the Climate High-resolution grid for the UK at 100m resolution and composited over daily and monthly timescales. They contain the aerosol optical depth and the fine-mode aerosol optical depth at 550nm. Two versions of each variable are included: with and without the post-processing filtering that is used in the global dataset.

Product name and acronym	Filename example	Version
SU Daily CHUK Aerosol SLSTR L3C	20171231-C3S-L3C_AEROSOL-AER_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3A-SU_DAILY_CHUK-v1.14.nc 20181231-C3S-L3C_AEROSOL-AER_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3B-SU_DAILY_CHUK-v1.14.nc	1.14
SU Monthly CHUK Aerosol SLSTR L3C	201712-C3S-L3C_AEROSOL-AER_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3A-SU_MONTHLY_CHUK-v1.14.nc 201812-C3S-L3C_AEROSOL-AER_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3B-SU_MONTHLY_CHUK-v1.14.nc	1.14

Table 1 Dataset Products covered in this document

1.2 Summary information

The datasets are available from the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (<https://dx.doi.org/10.5285/061fc86521c24c32b2b29aea08080195/>) where the corresponding global datasets are also available (<https://dx.doi.org/10.5285/17d83baf50a644d89a4fb78ca6cccec1>). These are described in detail in the journal paper (Pearson, K. *et al.*, 2025, Atmospheric aerosol measurements from the ATSR-SLSTR series of dual-view satellite instruments 1995–2022, *Sci Data*, **12**, 410 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04694-6>)

Product Name	SU Daily Aerosol SLSTR CHUK L3C
Main observed variable(s)	Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm, Fine Mode Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm
Geographical range of dataset	15.37°<lon<4.75°, 47.09°<lat<61.14°
Temporal range of dataset	SLSTR-A: 2016/05/01-2025/03/31 SLSTR-B: 2018/05/09-2025/03/31
Spatial resolution / gridding	100mx100m
Temporal sampling characteristics	Daily
Level of processing	L3C Gridded Data
Dataset citation	doi:10.5285/ccf69c5ea5184721906eb312d37d0673

Table 2 Summary Information for SU Daily Aerosol SLSTR CHUK L3C dataset

Product Name	SU Monthly Aerosol SLSTR CHUK L3C
Main observed variable(s)	Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm, Fine Mode Aerosol Optical Depth at 550nm
Geographical range of dataset	15.37°<lon<4.75°, 47.09°<lat<61.14°
Temporal range of dataset	SLSTR-A: 2016/05-2024/12 SLSTR-B: 2018/05-2024/12
Spatial resolution / gridding	100mx100m
Temporal sampling characteristics	Monthly
Level of processing	L3C Gridded Data
Dataset citation	doi:10.5285/96388e7a347b4a5fa287f012eb5d6920

Table 3 Summary Information for SU Monthly Aerosol SLSTR CHUK L3C dataset

1.2.1 Variables summary information

Variable name	Description	Units
x	Easting	m
y	Northing	m
AOD550_mean	Mean aerosol optical thickness at 550nm	Dimensionless
FM_AOD550_mean	Fine mode AOD	Dimensionless
AOD550_fltr_mean	Mean aerosol optical thickness at 550nm with post-retrieval filtering	Dimensionless
FM_AOD550_fltr_mean	Fine mode AOD with post-retrieval filtering	Dimensionless

Table 4 Summary information for each variable included in all the datasets.

1.3 What can these products be used for?

These products form a long-term set of observations of global aerosol optical depth. Such observations are required to reduce the current large range in the estimated radiative forcing associated with aerosol effects. The products can be used to infer regional aerosol optical depth trends as part of climate monitoring. They can also be used as inputs to numerical weather and climate modelling seeking to include the radiative effects of aerosols.

1.4 Where to find these products for download

To access the dataset product(s) navigate to the following location:
<https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/061fc86521c24c32b2b29aea08080195/>

1.5 Using downloaded data

All data files are provided in NetCDF format and accessible with standard tools. Example python code to ingest, subset, regrid and display mapped data is given below.

1.5.1 Import Data

This sample code uses the xarray module to import a sample dataset and show the contents.

Example Code:

```
import xarray as xr

# Open an AOD Monthly dataset
filename = '202109-EOCIS-L3C_AEROSOL-AER_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3A-SU_MONTHLY_CHUK-
v1.14.nc'

d = xr.open_dataset(filename)
d
```

Illustrative Results:

```
<xarray.Dataset> Size: 3GB
Dimensions:                (x: 10970, bnds: 2, y: 15170)
Coordinates:
  * x                       (x) int32 44kB -331950 -331850 ... 764850 764950
  * y                       (y) int32 61kB 1249950 1249850 ... -266850 -266950
Dimensions without coordinates: bnds
Data variables:
  x_bnds                    (x, bnds) int32 88kB ...
  y_bnds                    (y, bnds) int32 121kB ...
  AOD550_mean              (y, x) float32 666MB ...
  FM_AOD550_mean          (y, x) float32 666MB ...
  AOD550_fltr_mean        (y, x) float32 666MB ...
  FM_AOD550_fltr_mean     (y, x) float32 666MB ...
Attributes: (12/41)
  Conventions:             CF-1.6
  naming_authority:       uk.ac.su.aatsraerosol
  title:                  SU aerosol product CHUK grid level 3
```

```
product_version: 1.0
sensor: SLSTR
platform: Sentinel-3A
...
geospatial_lat_units: metres
geospatial_lon_units: metres
geospatial_lat_resolution: 100
geospatial_lon_resolution: 100
inputfilelist: ['20210901-EOCIS-L3C_AEROSOL-AER_PRODUCTS-SLS...
summary: This dataset contains the level-3 monthly mea...
```

1.5.2 Data Reduction/Subsetting

This sample code makes a subset of the dataset loaded in the previous subsection, takes a subset and shows the contents of the new data structure.

Example Code:

```
subset=d.AOD550_mean.sel(x=slice(-10000,5000), y=slice(10000,-7500))
subset
```

Illustrative Results:

```
<xarray.DataArray 'AOD550_mean' (y: 175, x: 150)> Size: 105kB
[26250 values with dtype=float32]
Coordinates:
  * x          (x) int32 600B -9950 -9850 -9750 -9650 ... 4650 4750 4850 4950
  * y          (y) int32 700B 9950 9850 9750 9650 9550 ... -7150 -7250 -7350 -7450
Attributes:
  valid_min:      0.0
  valid_max:      4.0
  standard_name:  atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol
  long_name:      aerosol optical thickness at 550 nm
```

1.5.3 Re-Gridding/Formatting

This code takes the subset formed in the previous subsection, performs a coarsening by binning at 4 times the previous resolution and then shows the resulting data structure.

Example Code:

```
# Regridding to a coarser spatial resolution (4x coarser)
subset_coarse = subset.coarsen(lon=4, lat=4, boundary='pad').mean()
subset_coarse
```

Illustrative Results:

```
<xarray.DataArray 'AOD550_mean' (y: 44, x: 38)> Size: 7kB
array([[0.09721664, 0.09731032, 0.0987155 , ..., 0.1017234 , 0.1017234 ,
```

```

    0.1017234 ],
    [0.0951484 , 0.09768504, 0.0987155 , ..., 0.11492603, 0.10883251,
     0.10397747],
    [0.06369218, 0.07560743, 0.08643941, ..., 0.11797278, 0.11797278,
     0.11228251],
    ...,
    [0.09935901, 0.10127129, 0.10191748, ..., 0.08524839, 0.08327421,
     0.08100647],
    [0.10065106, 0.10248706, 0.10251261, ..., 0.08725595, 0.09187611,
     0.09187611],
    [0.10223016, 0.10335062, 0.10335062, ..., 0.08817998, 0.09187611,
     0.09187611]], dtype=float32)
Coordinates:
  * x          (x) float64 304B -9.8e+03 -9.4e+03 -9e+03 ... 4.6e+03 4.9e+03
  * y          (y) float64 352B 9.8e+03 9.4e+03 9e+03 ... -7e+03 -7.35e+03
Attributes:
  valid_min:      0.0
  valid_max:      4.0
  standard_name:  atmosphere_optical_thickness_due_to_ambient_aerosol
  long_name:      aerosol optical thickness at 550 nm

```

1.5.4 Forming a Time-series

The data files do not contain a time dimension but this can be deduced either from the file names or the metadata. The following code uses the numpy, xarray and matplotlib modules to read the 12 monthly data files for year, add a time dimension and then plot the mean AOD within a geographic sub-region against time.

Example Code:

```

import xarray as xr
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Set the year and filename parameters
yyyy='2021'
filebase = '-EOCIS-L3C_AEROSOL-AER_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3A-SU_MONTHLY_CHUK-
v1.14.nc'

# Loop over months in the year
for m in np.arange(1,13):
    # Create the filename for this month
    mm="{:02d}".format(m)
    filename=yyyy+mm+filebase
    # Load the file
    d = xr.open_dataset(filename)
    #Add a "month" dimension of length 1 and make it a coordinate with this month's
    value
    d=d.expand_dims(dim={"Month": 1 } )
    d=d.assign_coords(Month=("Month", [m] ) )
    #Append the new data along the Month dimension
    if (m == 1):

```

```

        d_total=d
    else:
        d_total=xr.combine_by_coords([d_total, d],combine_attrs='drop_conflicts')
#End the month loop

#Find the mean value of AOD across the spatial dimensions
AODvTime=d_total.AOD550_mean.mean(dim=["x","y"])

#Make a figure and assign month names to the x-axis
fig=plt.figure()
ax=fig.add_subplot(1,1,1)
AODvTime.plot()
mnths=["Jan", "Feb", "Mar", "Apr", "May", "Jun", "Jul", "Aug", "Sep", "Oct", "Nov", "Dec"]
ax.set_xticks(range(1,13),mnths)
plt.title("Mean SLSTR-A AOD in the UK region during 2019")

#Display the figure
plt.show()

```


Figure 1 Time-series of mean AOD in the UK region during 2019 from SLSTR-A data

1.5.5 Displaying Data

This code makes use of the matplotlib, cartopy, pylab, netCDF4 and numpy python modules to produce a map of the global dataset with overlaid continents.

Example Code:

```

import matplotlib.pylab as plt
import matplotlib.colors as colors
import cartopy.crs as ccrs
import netCDF4
import numpy as np

```

```
# A function to redefine the colormap to remove the darkest blues
def truncate_colormap(cmap, minval=0.0, maxval=1.0, n=256):
    new_cmap = colors.LinearSegmentedColormap.from_list(
        'trunc({n},{a:.2f},{b:.2f})'.format(n=cmap.name, a=minval, b=maxval),
        cmap(np.linspace(minval, maxval, n)))
    return new_cmap

# Load the data using the netCDF interface
filename='201806-EOCIS-L3C_AEROSOL-AER_PRODUCTS-SLSTR_SENTINEL_S3A-SU_MONTHLY_CHUK-
v1.14.nc'
aod=netCDF4.Dataset(filename).variables['AOD550_mean'][:]

# Increase the default font size and lighten the colour mapping
plt.rcParams.update({'font.size': 12})
cmap = plt.get_cmap('jet')
new_cmap=truncate_colormap(cmap,0.15,1.0)

# Create the plotting area
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(10,7))
ax=fig.add_subplot(1,1,1)
ax.set_title('SLSTR-A Monthly Mean AOD 2018-06')

# Add the data to the map
im=ax.imshow(aod, vmin=0.0, vmax=0.5, cmap=new_cmap)
plt.colorbar(im, label='Aerosol Optical Depth',orientation='vertical')

# Display the figure
plt.show()
```


Figure 2 Example Monthly Mean AOD field from SLSTR-A

1.6 Your obligations when using these products

By accessing the Swansea University Aerosol Optical Depth products, you agree to cite the dataset digital object identifier (doi) and corresponding journal article describing the dataset every time you publish results obtained in whole or in part by use of UK EOCIS products. These citations are given under Summary Information.

The reference to the dataset should mention "created by the UK Earth Observation Climate Information Service". The product name and acronym in Table 1 should be used to avoid confusion and enable traceability.

History of modifications / Change Log

Version	Date	Changes	Person
0.2	10/02/2025	Initial Draft	Kevin Pearson
1.0	18/05/2026	Initial Published Version	Kevin Pearson

Related Documents / Reference Documents

Document	Author	Reference

Acronyms and/or Abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Definition
AOD	Aerosol Optical Depth
SLSTR	Sea and Land Surface Radiometer

General definitions

Term	Definition